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MEDICAL REFORMS ON STRENGTHENING THE GENEFOUND OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the implementation of a number of regulatory documents adopted by the industry, work to improve the state of the gene pool, as well as the reproductive health of the population in our country in recent years.

Keywords: *medical service, reforms in the healthcare system, public health, gene pool of the population, medical products.*

Introduction. In recent years, the quality of medical services provided to the population in our country has been radically improved, and complex measures aimed at improving the resource potential of medical institutions are being implemented. In order to systematically and qualitatively organize the rapid development of the national health system, general practice doctors, patronage medical nurses, rural medical centers, urgent and emergency medical services, and at the same time, to bring the country's health care system to a new level in terms of quality. In the conditions where it is necessary to raise, the issues of introducing an innovative model of management of the medical field are in the center of attention of the state.

In the past period, the system of providing primary medical and sanitary care was improved by establishing rural medical centers, urban and rural family polyclinics, and the population's opportunities to use these services were expanded. A unified centralized system of emergency medical care has been created, the network of

republican specialized scientific-practical medical centers providing high-tech medical care to citizens, including on-site, is being improved. [1, C.19-23].

Results. Development of smart medicine begins in Uzbekistan. This is defined as one of the main tasks of the Ministry of Innovative Development. The Ministry of Innovative Development promotes the accelerated development of the healthcare system by introducing the concepts of "Smart Medicine" and "Unified Medical Information Center", including advanced technologies that provide early detection and remote prevention of diseases, taking into account world standards. It is being reported [2].

In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 1, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the private sector in the field of health care" No. PQ-2863 [3], further development of the private sector of health care wide-scale work was carried out aimed at creating favorable conditions for the activities of private medical organizations, improving the system of regulating and licensing their activities, and encouraging the increase in the volume and types of services provided.

Over the past period, the types of medical services provided by the private sector of health care have increased from 50 to 126. Until January 1, 2022, private medical organizations, except stomatology and cosmetology organizations, were exempted from paying all types of taxes and mandatory deductions, as well as customs fees for imported new medical equipment, components, their spare parts and necessary materials [4].

At the same time, the transfer of some functions of state medical institutions to the private sector of health care, the development of public-private partnerships in this field, as well as the improvement of the qualifications of medical personnel in the republic and abroad, and the introduction of the system of accreditation of medical organizations remain relevant.

On December 29, 2017, in order to further stimulate the development of the private sector of health care, improve the conditions for training, retraining and

upgrading the qualifications of personnel, as well as to further expand the volumes of medical services provided, to attract investments in the private medical sector. The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On creating additional conditions for the further development of private medical organizations" was adopted [5].

In 2019-2025, the concept of health system development in the Republic of Uzbekistan was developed. The main goals of the concept are:

1. Increasing life expectancy by improving the prevention and treatment of diseases and situations that lead to premature death and disability in most cases;
2. Reforming the system of financing and organization of health care to ensure cheap use of medical care, financial protection of the population and fair distribution of resources;
3. Strengthen the capacity of health management bodies, increase the role and responsibility of their leaders in order to fulfill the tasks of the concept and improve the quality of medical care provided to the population of the republic [6, B. 70-71].

Structural changes were made in the pharmaceutical industry, tax and customs incentives were given to local manufacturers, and free economic zones were established for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry.

The future of every nation is closely related to the health of its children and the purity of its offspring. In our country, all conditions are being created for the health of children, for them to flourish and grow like in a brochure. Our state spares neither attention nor funds in this regard. On December 25, 2017, the President signed the Decision "On the State program for the early detection of congenital and hereditary diseases in children in the period 2018-2022" [9].

It can be said that this document was one of the important steps in thinking about the future of our country, the generation of our people, and the "purity of our flag". In fact, since the first days of independence, protection of motherhood and childhood in our country has been defined as one of the strategic directions of the state social policy.

The quality of medical care provided to women and children of reproductive age, including the organization of:

- reproductive health and safe motherhood, perinatal diagnostic offices (maternal screening), as well as children's departments in multidisciplinary polyclinics of the central district (city); providing round-the-clock emergency medical care to children due to the expansion of emergency pediatric brigades and emergency posts in children's inpatient institutions;

- by establishing a system of diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of children suffering from hereditary, genetic, primary immunodeficiency, congenital and acquired diseases, including rehabilitation centers for children suffering from congenital, chronic diseases and disabilities improvement;

- implementation of early assistance programs for children who are prone to hereditary diseases and belong to the risk group;

- national projects aimed at reducing child mortality and disability, including "Integrated Management of Childhood Diseases", "Child Injuries and Child Abuse", which support the physical and psychosocial well-being of adolescents. Implementation of the programs "Health of babies", "Health of teenagers", "Physical education and sports", "Formation of a healthy school environment";

- Extensive use of modern methods and programs of study of school-aged children used by the World Health Organization, "Health Behavior Survey of School-aged Children" (HBSC) European cooperation network and Epidemiological control of childhood obesity Uzbekistan's joining the European network (COSI) for the further improvement of specialized high-tech, including microsurgery, for mothers and children;

- Establishment of large multidisciplinary medical centers "Mother and Child" on the basis of public-private partnership conditions, including by unification of low-efficiency and narrowly specialized public medical organizations [1, C.15-20], etc.

Conclusion. Most importantly, modern medical services are being introduced to the population, necessary conditions are being created for patients, and modern

technical equipment necessary for medicine and medicine is being provided. Hospitals in the republic are being fully renovated and medical services are being provided according to world standards. Thanks to this, the concept of "Healthy mother, healthy child" and the national model of mother and child health protection were created in our country.

In recent years, in order to achieve the long-term effect of improving the gene pool of our nation, improving the medical culture in the family, the quality of life of the population, and achieving a long life, a consistent measure has been taken to create favorable conditions for the birth of a healthy generation and its upbringing. - events have been implemented.

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